

Future of Teacher Education in the Context of NEP 2020

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Abstract: In India, the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has announced the New Educational Policy in 2020 which aims to bring changes to the education system. Since its Independence government of India came out with various policies and committees to improve the quality and standard of Teacher Education. The new NEP 2020 has brought a tremendous change in the field of teacher education to make it more transparent and qualitative. The main objective of the paper is to highlight the new guidelines of NEP 2020 related to Teacher Education. The paper outlines the newly added courses and restructuring of the existing courses and their integration with the bachelor's degrees which will benefit the in-service as well as pre-service teachers in near future. NEP's future approaches and recruitment procedures for Teacher and Teacher Education are also highlighted in the paper. The paper also outlines the opportunities where people belonging to rural areas and geographically isolated areas can also fulfill their dreams to become a teacher by profession. Teacher Education will be more strengthened and transparent in the manner with the new policy. The accountability of the Institutions providing Teacher Education has been put under strong supervision as per the new NEP 2020. The paper also briefly highlights the significance of Teacher Education and how people of other specializations can opt for the courses with proper training. Importance of local people's knowledge and making it a part of Teacher Education is also included in the paper. Overall, the continuation and procedure of Teacher Education in near future according to the National Educational Policy 2020 is outlined in the paper.

Keywords: Education, Teacher Education, B.Ed. and National Educational Policy 2020

Introduction

“A great teacher is both made and born. Teaching is a skill which has to be acquired and proper training makes one skillful”.

One can say that teachers are born with talent and a passion for teaching and further they are also made by enhancing their talent and developing new skills. For the enhancement of such skills, Teacher Education has to be more advanced. Teacher Education refers to the process of nurturing a teacher with proper skills, knowledge, attitude, and behavior to make them work in the classroom and outside efficiently and effectively. Since its independence, the Government of India has made every possible effort to develop the condition of Teacher Education with an effective suggestion, recommendations, and the establishment of various bodies like the University Grants Commission (UGC), National Council of Educational Research and Training (SCERT), National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) and National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE). Among these, NAAC has its own importance in Teacher Education by focusing on quality in higher education. Organizing seminars, workshops, and conferences to improve the quality of education played its role well. The watershed event made by NCTE was to include Information and Communication Technology (ICT) enduringly in the B.Ed. curriculum.

The significance of Teacher Education in India cannot be overemphasized. They are the ones to imbibe ethical values and principles in students, thereby helping in nation-building. Teacher's education makes the teachers competent to face any challenges and prevent failure. It helps the teachers to choose the authentic learning materials and a way of teaching. As teaching prepares future teachers, Teacher Education should be effectively mentored to set with the new situation. Effective Teacher Education helps the one to swiftly adopt new techniques and innovation from time to time.

How did National Educational Policy 2020 come into existence?

Since its Independence, the government of India has set up many planning commissions with an objective to achieve Universal elementary education, increase literacy, the establishment of the vocational skillful training program, and modernize the education system. On the recommendation given by the Kothari Commission the first National Policy of Education (NPE), 1968 was announced. The policy aimed at the maximum distribution of educational opportunities for higher national, cultural, and economic development. The teaching of regional language, 10+2+3 structure, and compulsory education for children below the age of

14 was the contribution of NPE 1968 only. After 18 years of halt, comes the second educational policy i.e., National Educational Policy 1986. This policy specially focused on Scheduled Tribe, Scheduled Caste, and Women Education. The introduction of scholarships benefits to poor by sending their children to schools, recruiting teachers from the SC category, and establishing a new institution was given to achieve the above aim. To improve the condition further distance and open learning were facilitated, e.g. Indira Gandhi National Open University. Certain modification to NPE 1986 was done according to the need of the hour i.e. proposal for the establishment of 20 new universities, stipend to research scholars, common entrance examinations all over the country, etc.

After all such measures there still lies a loophole in the education system of India. According to a survey conducted by NCERT, the performance of students in many states is below average level and the Indian Education System was facing a big challenge then. This survey was the largest conducted in the Country as well as the world. The survey was done aiming to understand how the school in India running and what is the level of student learning. This survey has shaken the country's expectation that millions of students could lose learning opportunities and the level of illiteracy would have increased if proper action was not taken immediately.

After 30 years of long gap comes the National Education Policy 2020 considering the earlier success and failure of the policies. This policy has brought a total transformation in the vision of the education structure and level of India. This policy has brought changes with it which the country required for a long. As India is a land of diverse cultures and languages, this policy has considered diversity while making the report. This policy specifically focuses on equitable, accessible, and Inclusive education. India will be able to touch the highest standard of education globally if NEP 2020 is implemented with full participation and cooperation of the Central and State governments, NGOs, Local bodies, and communities.

New guidelines and actions on Teacher Education as per NEP 2020

National Education Policy 2020 laid much emphasis on nurturing teachers by imbibing Indian culture, knowledge, values, and ethos in them. At the same time emphasis should be given to the innovation and advancements in the field of education and pedagogy. The NEP 2020 in its report highlighted the loopholes that exist in Teacher Education. Several thousands of Teacher Education Institutions in India are not imparting adequate and qualitative training and education to the teacher. The valuable degrees are weighted and sold at the cost of a high rate of money which is a setback on the part of the nation's future building. The government has taken several measures to reduce the malpractices and improve the quality of Teacher Education but none can flatten the curb. To bring a balance to the system, credibility, integrity, and quality have to be restored first. To meet these needs a stringent step for those non-standard institutions providing Teacher Education will be taken. The system of regulation will be given more power and a free hand to take action against dysfunctional Teacher Education Institutions. The Teacher Education institution will be bound to follow the minimum prescribed criteria within one year, failing to meet the criteria may lead to the dissolution of the Institution. As per the guidelines of NEP 2020, Institution and education programs with quality, multidisciplinary, and integrated with nature will be in force.

All the Universities and colleges multidisciplinary in nature should have an objective for the establishment of educational departments, collaboration with other departments of different disciplines, and facilitating B.Ed. programme in it. The existing Teacher Education Institution providing a two-year B.Ed. programme will also have to shift to a multidiscipline institution providing four-years integrated Teacher Education by 2030. By 2030 this four-year course of B.Ed. shall be the minimum criteria for the qualification of school teachers. The Teacher Education programme will get broader in the area and cover more specialization including early childhood care and foundational literacy. Teachers belonging to other streams outside education can also enroll in B.Ed. programme for two years. Teacher Education as per NEP 2020 laid much emphasis on nurturing teachers by imbibing Indian culture, values, traditions, knowledge, and ethos. At the same time, the higher education institutions enabling Teacher Education should fulfill the need for experts in every discipline provided by the institution. Any teacher before admission to the Teacher Education programme will have to pass through a subject aptitude test conducted by National Testing Agency. These qualified institutions providing Teacher Education need to create a strong base with the schools to enable the teachers to engage in different activities. Besides, training and teacher with research experience will be highly valued. In the case of Ph.D., the researcher during their training period have to opt for a course on a credit basis in subjects like writing, teaching, pedagogy, and education. To assure the new scholars have mastery over their chosen discipline when becoming a faculty in the future, exploration in curriculum designing and pedagogical practices will be included during the training. The newly Ph.D. entrants have to grow through teaching assistantship and acquire required teaching experience in universities.

The existing teachers in universities and colleges will continue with more strengthened initiatives to meet the demand of the teaching-learning process. The advancement in the teaching-learning process will be met through

online platforms like SWAYAM and DIKSHA. This process will reach out to several numbers of trainees in a shorter period of time. The overall mentoring initiative will be taken at a PAN India level by the experts and retired faculty to facilitate an extra push to universities and colleges faculties in India.

Adoption of Placement procedures, standards, and approaches toward Teachers and the Teaching Profession

In terms of recruitment, only capable and outstanding students will be allowed to enter the profession laying much weightage on rural areas students. To make deserving students receive quality Teacher Education i.e., four-year B.Ed. programme, an adequate merit-based scholarship will be provided throughout the country. The teacher after completing the courses will be employed in their local ground which will treat as a role model for the rest section of the society. The eligibility criteria before recruiting them will be more strengthened. The recruited teachers will be kept engaged in teaching activities rather than non-teaching activities which existed till then so that the novel approaches of teachers can secure learning outcomes in the classroom.

To measure the standards of the teaching profession NCTE will act as Professional Standard Setting Body (PSSB) to set the common guidelines of National Profession Standards for Teachers (NPST) by 2022 NCTE in collaboration with NCERT and SCERT will work under the General Educational Council, experts across the country in the field of higher education, teacher preparation, and vocational education will also be a part of the process. To make Teacher Education cop up with the innovation and methods, the design of the pre-service Teacher Education programme will be redesigned and modified from time to time by the NPST.

There will be an up-gradation in the approaches to Teacher Education. By 2030, Teacher Education will be shifted to multidisciplinary colleges and universities to ensure qualitative training and pedagogy. The newly converted multidisciplinary colleges and universities will have to start the establishment of new education departments by facilitating bachelor's, Masters and Ph.D. degrees. The four-year bachelor's degree will become the minimum criteria for teaching by 2030 which will involve high-level training for the student-teacher at local level schools. The same colleges and universities will also facilitate the existing two-year bachelor's degree besides the four-year program. This two-year B.Ed. can be received by those who have their bachelor's degrees in other subjects and are willing to become a teacher. One year B.Ed. program can be received by those who already have received equivalent degrees like 4 years B.Ed. or master degree and willing to become a teacher in the specific subject. The new policy will also provide opportunities to remote area students to acquire this four-year B.Ed. programme, this programme will be available in a blended mode so that it gets accessed to the remote areas. From now onwards, the curriculum B.Ed. programme will include awareness and conservation of the environment and environment education. Special courses of shorter duration like BITEs and DIET will also be available at local premises as Teacher Education programme where local people with higher knowledge and skills can work as master instructors for promoting local professions like arts, crafts, music, and vocational crafts, etc.

The new policy has been made taking physically challenged into consideration where the teacher who wishes to deal with such special students can do so by acquiring post B.Ed. courses in a shorter time frame. These courses will be made available in all colleges and universities multidisciplinary in nature. The same courses will also have other specializations like leadership and management in school positions. Any teacher can move from the foundational stage to preparatory, middle, and secondary by receiving this post B.Ed. course. Overall, to assure the implementation of all the measures in the education system stringent action will be set against those sub-standard institutions.

How NEP 2020 can be successfully implemented?

The successful implementation of the NEP 2020 depends on the stakeholders involved in the entire process and without proper incentives, the process cannot be smoother. The credibility of stakeholders should be developed through their transparent actions and participation. The principles of management should be made more sound to achieve the desired results. Learning should become more practical and experimental to develop the level of creativity among children. Learning should become more holistic with the involvement of technology and digital learning. They make the policy successfully implemented, and both the center and the state government should cooperate and collaborate sharing the duties and responsibilities with each other.

Conclusion

It has been acknowledged that formed training is necessary for the development of skills in teachers. training helps in the development of teachers' personalities and the code of conduct. India is the second-largest country in terms of population in the world, it stands at 10th position from the bottom in terms of teachers per thousand children under the age of 15. The gap between the number of teachers and student is wide compared to other countries across the world. In terms of education, India stands at 59th position out of 64 countries which

clearly highlights the increased unemployment and challenges to quality education. It is an indication of the production of the unskilled youth which is a failure on the part of the teacher. To overcome the situation the new NEP 2020 will prove to be a strong stair to reach the destination. The National Education Policy 2020 guidelines for Teacher Education will prove adequate to mitigate the obstacle that has to remain untouched. If the NEP 2020 guidelines are genuinely implemented in Indian teaching programme, colleges, and universities, the dream of our former national leader and educationist will turn into a reality where education will be qualitative in nature, and India with the second-largest population could stand at the highest position in term of Education.

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